

GEO MORPHOMETRY
PERUGIA ITALY

2025
JUNE 9-13

Geomorphometry in the Cloud: New Capabilities and Future Directions of ArcGIS

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Abstract— Over the last decade, the geospatial user community and Esri have moved toward increasing use of cloud hosted data and analysis provided as web services. Most GIS usage now relies to some extent on web services. ArcGIS provides an integrated system of desktop and cloud-hosted software and services. The desktop application was designed from inception with web services integration in mind, to provide a comprehensive yet simple experience to publish and consume web services. It is now possible to perform a complete GIS analysis project in the cloud, and we anticipate increasing use of fully cloud-hosted research and applications. This paper provides a brief overview of the components of that system and their use. Esri is an active partner in the geomorphometry community and here additionally provides an update on relevant recent developments, focusing on new and improved algorithms, and computational performance.

I. GEOMORPHOMETRY IN THE CLOUD

Esri provides a fully cloud hosted geomorphometry platform in ArcGIS Online, a complete Software as a Service (SaaS) platform to collect, explore, analyze, visualize, and share spatial data services, and develop web map applications. It includes a rich collection of open global terrain data, online processing to collect and build terrain data, geomorphometry analysis services, and terrain visualization. ArcGIS Online provides a place for users to publish their data as web services to share with others, from within ArcGIS Online or from ArcGIS Pro. No knowledge of web services or cloud hosting is required. Analogous to how people share videos by uploading to YouTube and other video hosting services, ArcGIS users share data and analysis through ArcGIS Online as web services. The SaaS infrastructure relies upon leading global hosting partners to provide performance, data residency, and redundancy. The system is used by over 650,000

organizations with several million users, supporting over 3 billion requests per day.

A. Terrain Data Services

ArcGIS Online hosts over 20 million data layers, including a curated collection of open and community contributed elevation from more than 60 organizations. This is nearly 150 Tb of lossless compressed gridded elevation data at multiple resolutions, including global coverage (minus a few restricted countries) of the Airbus 24-meter WorldDEM4Ortho, and over 27 million km² of 50-centimeter resolution Maxar Precision 3D. The terrain data is available as web services for visualization and analysis in a variety of ArcGIS client applications including ArcGIS Pro and can also be downloaded for offline analysis. Users can upload their elevation to ArcGIS Online and publish as web services for their use, grant access to others in their organization, or provide fully open access.

B. ArcGIS Online Raster Analytics

The full suite of GIS and image analysis capabilities, including terrain analysis are available in ArcGIS Online, providing hosted compute in a secure environment. The user has access to scalable server setups where they can run raster analysis tools and functions [Fig.1]. Analysis outputs are hosted in the users' ArcGIS Online account and immediately available as image services.

In contrast to ArcGIS Enterprise - which also allows for scalability in a secure environment, in ArcGIS Online, Esri provides the infrastructure including setup and maintenance, as well as data hosting. Available tools and functions include terrain and hydrologic analysis tools to characterize terrain, define viewsheds and extract hydrologic information from surface rasters.

Figure 1. The Surface Parameters raster function dialog in ArcGIS Online provides access to slope, aspect, and 7 geometric curvatures.

C. Ready to Use Services

For common analysis tasks on widely used datasets, ArcGIS provides a collection of Ready to Use services, combining source data and cloud-optimized analysis. They are accessible in ArcGIS Pro, ArcGIS Online, and via REST API. For hydrologic analysis these include watershed delineation and downstream tracing where the user provides only the initiation location [1]. The source data is built from 90m SRTM globally and 30m NHD in the United States, which have been further hydroconditioned, and optimized for fast compute. The user provides only the starting locations points, and result polygons or lines are returned in 15-30 seconds as hosted feature services. Visibility analysis, elevation summary statistics, and elevation profile services are also provided for a wide range of elevation sources and resolutions. These services simplify the user experience, save ArcGIS users thousands of hours of processing, and are provided at no cost.

D. Scalable Analytics

In recent years Esri has put considerable effort into keeping algorithms up to date leveraging rapidly advancing computing architectures. This work includes parallel algorithms for multicore desktops and single nodes, GPU-specific implementations, optimizations for distributed computation across many nodes, and a cloud-native Kubernetes version. Kubernetes is an open-source technology for managing and scaling containerized applications in the cloud. ArcGIS on Kubernetes testing included raster data of nearly 4 trillion pixels and 400 CPUs.

More than 300 analysis tools in ArcGIS run parallel, and 40 of those have GPU specific implementations. This includes the frequently used land-surface parameter tools and hydrology tools. For example, running hydrologic analysis tools on the full global 30m DEM, over 540 billion cells, in Kubernetes with 40 nodes / 200 pods completes FlowDirection in 4.4 hours, where a single processor machine would require 14 days. The ArcGIS geoprocessing analysis environment provides options for the user to control how many processors to use and when to use CPU or GPU computation. New analysis tools are designed for parallel distributed computation from inception and also evaluated for their GPU suitability and benefit.

II. NEW CAPABILITIES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

A. Geodesic Algorithms

Many geomorphometry indices use distances and angles as part of their computation, e.g. slope, curvature. A significant percentage of DEMs and other geospatial data are provided in spherical coordinates (latitude / longitude) where there is a difference in the length of a degree in X and Y. To accommodate measuring distances and angles, softwares used a conversion factor to compensate for this difference or required reprojection to a planar coordinate system. We agree with Guth and Kane [2] this approach is outdated and introduces unacceptable bias. To remove problems of planar algorithms applied to spherical data, more than 40 ArcGIS tools were rewritten using spherical math, including calculations of slope, aspect, curvatures, visibility, solar radiation, and more. Future analysis tools computing distance are designed for both planar and geodesic implementations.

The new curvature implementation expanded the list of available curvatures types to include 7 geometric curvatures following the math and clarity of naming conventions of Minár et al [3, 4].

B. Landscape Scale

Terrain processes occur at a range of scales and terrain data is available at a range of spatial resolutions. Deriving terrain metrics from high resolution data over large areas drove the earlier mentioned efforts improving algorithm performance and scalability. Traditional geomorphometric moving window algorithms typically used only the immediate 3x3 neighborhood of values. This worked well for modeling common landform processes with commonly available data of 10m to 90m resolution. However higher resolution data of 1 meter and finer require different consideration. For a land planning application, is the slope at 1 meter resolution important or is the slope at 10-meter resolution more useful? To accommodate such applications ArcGIS now allows the user to specify a desired window size for their calculations. An auto-adaptive window size is also provided which uses local terrain variance to determine an appropriate window size.

The adaptive window is particularly useful when there are widely varying sizes of terrain features of interest, such as small gullies and large plateaus in the study area.

ArcGIS Pro 3.4 also includes several multiscale tools developed in collaboration with John Lindsay of Whitebox GeoSpatial Inc. The new multiscale tools characterize terrain in terms of elevation difference and percentile values [Fig.2], measuring how they respond to changes in scale. Scales are identified using neighborhood distances. The user can specify a minimum and a maximum, and an increment to control the increase in neighborhood distance. Analyzing different scales allows to find the most extreme values and identify prominent landscape features.

Figure 2. Inputs and output (d) of a streamline index model for identifying most likely stream paths. In addition to flow accumulation the model uses (a) Geomorphons, (b) Planform (projected contour) curvature, and (c) Multiscale elevation percentile.

C. Hydrology

ArcGIS hydrologic analysis capabilities cover a wide range: from fundamental tools (ArcGIS Spatial Analyst) to application-oriented (Arc Hydro) and decision-support tools (flood simulation).

ArcGIS Spatial Analyst includes foundational tools to address fundamental problems. These include preparing a DEM for hydrologic analysis, extracting hydrologic information such as watersheds, streams or storage capacity, and characterizing stream information in terms of connectivity and order. More recent tools allow for hydrologic information extraction with minimal DEM modification [5] considering higher resolution DEMs which may contain a more realistic representation of terrain. For working with noisy high resolution terrains Feature Preserving Smoothing [6] was included at ArcGIS Pro 3.4.

Arc Hydro [7] is no-cost collection of more than 200 terrain and hydrologic analysis tools, and hydrologic data production and

modeling workflows. It is used to build foundational datasets for use in water resource analyses and for integration with water resource models. The underlying Arc Hydro data model standardizes water data structures so that data can be used consistently and efficiently to solve a wide range of water resource problems at any scale—regional, national, or international.

Flood simulation modeling was recently added to ArcGIS Pro. The simulation uses shallow water equations within a defined area of interest to model how water moves and accumulates on the landscape [8]. It is used in disaster scenario planning, and interactive visualization of flood impacts from changes in the landscape, urban development, or flood mitigation efforts. Typical use is to analyze the flooding impact through different scenarios created by changing relevant variables interactively. The process starts with creating one or more flood simulation layers in a scene, run the scenario, and review the visual results. Then create another scenario with parameter adjustments or changes to the landscape, such as increasing the rainfall or adding a dike or flood wall and visualize the change of impact.

D. Artificial Intelligence Integration

The use of geospatial artificial intelligence (GeoAI) modeling techniques has seen rapid growth in the geomorphometry community. Esri and its customers are using GeoAI for terrain hydroconditioning, wetland mapping [9], landslide risk [10], and a wide range of image feature extraction and spatial modeling tasks. To ease the learning curve and empower more people to use these capabilities, Esri provides direct integration with a large collection of deep learning models and toolkits. Additionally, Esri provides a collection of pretrained models [11] for common spatial tasks such as landcover mapping, change detection, disaster damage assessment, and a variety of other object detection.

Beyond analytic methods, Esri uses knowledge of its software best practices in customizing and training its own AI models to improve users' ability to find appropriate tools, compose workflows, and to assist in writing code.

E. Solar and Planetary Enhancements

Since the last Geomorphometry meeting Esri has replaced its solar radiation modeling tools. The new implementation computes in geodesic space, has both GPU and distributed CPU capabilities, and in collaboration with NASA was adapted to use the Moon's coordinate systems and planetary ephemeris to enable solar energy calculations for use in Moon rover route planning and Moon base site suitability modeling.

F. Partnering

Esri is an engaged collaborator in the geomorphometry community, following and promoting emerging research as well

as contributing. Work described above on geodesic calculations, curvatures, and adaptive window size are available as a standalone, open-source Jupyter notebook [12] for others to leverage in implementing new methods. For example if someone wanted to create a new moving window metric but lacked the time or skills to implement the geodesic math or adaptive window, those pieces are all available in the notebook.

Our recent collaboration with John Lindsay incorporates some of the novel work of Whitebox into ArcGIS as native tools (Feature Preserving Smoothing and the multiscale tools mentioned above). Implementing them as native tools in ArcGIS enables them to read and write all supported formats in ArcGIS, support the full analysis environment, and take advantage of our performance and scalability software framework.

III. EXTENDING ARCGIS

The geomorphometry research community is quite active in developing new methods, and applying them to relevant societal problems. To support this and other communities Esri provides an open, extensible system with numerous APIs and examples. Python is the primary scripting language of the geospatial community and has been the scripting language of ArcGIS for over 20 years. Python has been used by many developers to implement new algorithms, build solution-oriented toolboxes [13] or integrate entire software packages. In recent years use of R with ArcGIS has also increased with projects such as the FluvialGeomorph toolbox [14] leveraging Esri's R [15] and Python integration. In addition to approaches to integrate new tools and toolboxes, ArcGIS also includes APIs and templates for web mapping, web app development, mobile app development, game engine integration, and more.

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